

GENDER AND AGE DIFFERENCES IN TIME MANAGEMENT BEHAVIORS, PERCEIVED CONTROL OF TIME, AND LIFE SATISFACTION AMONG STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the gender and age differences in time management behaviors, perceived control of time, and life satisfaction among students. Time management is crucial for academic success and overall well-being. However, individual differences, including gender and age, may influence how effectively students manage their time, perceive their control over it, and ultimately, experience life satisfaction. In the current study a sample of 300 college and university students was collected. Time Management Self-Assessment Questionnaire (Olmstead, 2010), Perceived Control of Internal States Scale (Pallant, 2000) and Students' Life Satisfaction Scale (Huebner et al., 2022) were used for data collection. Results revealed that female students scored higher on time management behavior whereas male students scored higher on life satisfaction. Age differences revealed that adults were scored higher on time management behavior and life satisfaction as compared to adolescents. The current research findings identified the potential gender and age-related disparities in time management strategies and their impact on student life satisfaction.

Keywords: Time Management Behaviors, Perceived Control of Time, Life Satisfaction, Gender, Age.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past 20 years, there has been an increase in time management research (Boniwell & Osin, 2015). Because plans could be rapidly modified to deal with unexpected occurrences and this makes flexibility achievable, which is definitely vital to today's multitasking, fast-paced students, but it can also keep them from establishing efficient learning routines. If students do not develop beneficial habits like time management, perceived control of time, self-regulation, motivation, and metacognition, they are likely to do poorly and find it difficult to advance in the future (Baothman et al., 2018). Time management is the capacity to prioritize tasks, set goals, allot time for every job, and track the outcomes and the value of flexibility in time

management as well. Plans should be modified as necessary when other duties take precedence. Setting goals helps you stay focused on the ultimate result and change your priorities (Sharma & Sharma, 2022).

While Balduf (2009) noted that poor time management results in academic underachievement and is effective scheduling guarantees college students' higher academic accomplishment. In addition, he found that 67% of college students said that time management was the most crucial problem. Additionally, he discovered that self-reported time management indicate academic success, with shorter planning in particular predicting college students' grade point average.

George et al. (2008) agreed that efficient time management could be a crucial component of academic achievement. They discovered that academic success is significantly predicted by time management. Additionally, they discovered that time management is linked to both academic and personal performance. Likewise, McKean and Misra (2000) stated that tactics utilized by students to improve their time management skills are recommended as means of boosting academic performance. Moreover, they found a relationship between academic stress and time management. A study by Al-Hadhrami et al. (2014) found that between 40 and 70 percent of undergraduate students frequently put off their academic work.

According to a model practicing the three-time management components more often should eventually increase one's sense of control. A thinking of control over one's time allocation the conviction that one has mastery over an individuals' time is attained by goal-setting, scheduling, and organization. Despite the intuitive attraction of the routes and the advocacy of time management gurus, no scientific evidence has been done to directly help these assumptions. However, it makes sense to infer from the goalsetting literature that the self-efficacy of an individual in controlling their conduct is correlated with their goal-setting activity (Bandura & Locke, 2003). Thus, this study was initial to empirically examine the connection between time management practices and a sense of control over time. Additionally, the three components are thought to be reciprocally related to one another, as indicated by the reciprocal curving lines between the time management habits.

Pehlivan (2013) also found that students' grades were impacted by their ability to manage their time well. According to the report, students manage their time to a reasonable degree. In terms of the gender variable, female students outperform male students in terms of grades and time management. Bratti and Staffolani (2013) discovered how undergraduate students' academic performance was affected by both attending lectures and studying on their own. According to their findings, only lecture attendance has a positive correlation with

success in quantitative subjects like mathematics and economics. for the majority of other courses, it is negligible. Perceived control of time among students can vary based on gender and age. Research suggests that females may experience lower perceived control compared to males, potentially due to societal expectations and gender roles that can limit their autonomy and decision-making power (Thompson & Walker, 1989). Additionally, age can influence perceived control, with younger students potentially feeling less in control due to limited autonomy and dependence on parents or guardians (Eccles et al., 1993). However, these findings are not universal, and individual experiences and sociocultural factors can significantly impact these trends. Life satisfaction among students is also influenced by various factors, including gender and age. Studies have shown mixed results regarding gender differences, with some finding no significant disparities (Huebner et al., 2000), while others report higher life satisfaction in either males (Moksnes et al., 2013) or females (Jackson et al., 2014). A meta-analysis by Chen et al. (2020) suggests that national context may play a role in these inconsistencies. Age is also a significant factor, with research indicating that life satisfaction tends to decrease during adolescence and early adulthood due to increased academic and social pressures (Diener et al., 2018; Rimsha, 2024).

Methodology

Objectives

- To examine gender and age differences in time management behavior, perceived control of time and life satisfaction among students.

Sample

The study's sample consisted of 300 college and university students including both male and female students. To gather the data, a purposive sampling technique was employed. The participants ranged in age from 15 to 24 years.

Instruments

Socio-demographic information including gender, age, birth order, and family system were covered in the first section of the

questionnaire. The following scales were used. [1] The Time Management Self-Assessment Questionnaire (Olmstead, 2010) which has 53 items was used to measure time management skills. From 1 (never) to 5 (always), the scale was 5-point Likert type. The scale has acceptable reliability. [2] Perceived Control of Internal States Scale (Pallant, 2000) was used to measure perceived control of time, which has 18 items and was 5-point Likert-type answer pattern, with 5 representing strongly disagree and 1 representing strongly agree. The scale has acceptable reliability. [3] Students' Life Satisfaction Scale (Huebner et al., 2022) was a self-report questionnaire for students' life satisfaction. It is 6-point Likert-type scale with seven items and responses of 1 (strongly disagree), to 6 (strongly agree). The scale has acceptable reliability.

Procedure

This study used a cross-sectional research methodology to examine the gender and age differences in time management, perceived control of time and life satisfaction of students. The relevant university and college officials were contacted via the appropriate channel in order to collect data. Three hundred college and university students provided the data. Participants in each institute received a brief explanation of the questionnaire. Additionally, participants were requested to provide accurate answers and completed an informed consent form before to data collection. Moreover, the researchers made sure that data of all participant will kept private. Following data collection, the researcher expressed gratitude to the participants for their essential contributions.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study variables

Characteristics	n	%
Gender		
Men	145	48.0
Women	155	51.0
Age		
15-17	157	52.3
18-24	143	47.7
Family System		
Nuclear	225	75.0
Extended	75	25.0
Birth Order		
Eldest	95	31.0
Middle child	133	44.0
Youngest	70	23.0
Single child	1	.3
Twins	1	.3
Education		
Intermediate	152	50.7
BS	148	49.3

Table 1 reveals that number of male participants (n = 145, 48.0%) participated in the study compared to female participants (n = 155, 51.0%). The number of participants participated from the age category of 12-18 years is (n = 157, 52.3%) and from 18-24 years is (n = 143, 47.7%). Number of participants from nuclear family system is (n = 225, 75.0%) and from Extended is (n = 75,

25.0%). The number of participants from eldest birth order is (n = 95, 31.1%), middle child is (n = 133, 44.3%), youngest is (n = 70, 23%), only child is (n = 1, .3%) and twins is (n = 1, .3%). The number of participants participated from different education groups is, intermediate (n = 152, 50.7%) and BS is (n = 148, 49.3%).

Table 2: Mean Comparisons in Time Management Behavior, Perceived Control of Time and Life Satisfaction of Students Across Gender

Variables	Males		Females		t(298)	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD		
Time Management Behavior	146.37	9.25	148.24	9.19	2.75*	.20
Perceived Control of Time	18.54	3.73	18.59	4.88	.11	.01
Life Satisfaction	32.86	5.58	30.05	5.85	4.25*	.49

*p< .05

Table 2 shows mean comparisons in time management behavior, perceived control of time and life satisfaction of students across gender. Results indicated non-significant mean differences in perceived control of

time. Findings further showed that female participants exhibited higher score on time management behavior whereas male scored higher on life satisfaction as compared to male participants.

Table 3: Mean Comparisons in Time Management Behavior, Perceived Control of Time and Life Satisfaction of Students Across Age

Variables	Adolescents		Adults		t(298)	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD		
Time Management Behavior	143.22	7.21	147.12	8.18	2.23*	.67
Perceived Control of Time	17.32	3.41	19.02	4.62	.21	.21
Life Satisfaction	30.87	5.43	32.21	5.92	3.21*	.81

*p< .05

Table 3 shows mean comparisons in time management behavior, perceived control of time and life satisfaction of students across age. Findings revealed that adults were significantly higher in time management behavior and life satisfaction as compared to adolescents. Results indicate non-significant mean differences on perceived control of time.

moderate alpha reliability with Cronbach's alpha values of .70 and .72 (<.80). These findings suggest that the items on these scales are consistent and adequately measure their respective constructs (Khan et al., 2016).

Our results confirmed that female students possess stronger time management behavior whereas male scored higher on life satisfaction as compared to male participants. This gender gap in time management is in line with other research (Bonsaksen et al., 2017), which indicates that women are frequently better at managing their time and juggling a variety of obligations. In line with previous research (Bonsaksen et al., 2024; Sultana & Shakur, 2022), it has been found that being a woman and achieving high academic performance is associated with time management profiles of college students with better time management. Research suggests that, generally, male students tend to report slightly higher life satisfaction compared to female students, particularly during adolescence, while life satisfaction can also vary depending on age with some

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to investigate gender and age differences in time management behavior, perceived control of time and life satisfaction of college and university students. Three scales were used in this study to evaluate gender and age differences in time management practices, perceived control over their time and life satisfaction. Cronbach's alpha (α) was utilized to evaluate the reliability of these scales. Perceived Control of Internal States Scale showed satisfactory reliability, with Cronbach's α value of .75 (<.80). The Time Management Self-Assessment Questionnaire and Students' Life Satisfaction Scale showed

studies showing a potential dip in satisfaction during mid-adolescence across genders; however, these differences can be influenced by various factors and may not be consistent across all studies.

Based on current research findings, there is evidence to suggest that adult students generally exhibit better time management behaviors and report higher levels of life satisfaction compared to younger students; this is often attributed to increased maturity, clearer goals, and a stronger sense of responsibility in older learners. According to a popular theory, life satisfaction and age are like "U-shape," with people's degree of life pleasure increasing with age and then decreasing as they approach middle age Blanchflower et al. (1997). Studies have shown a positive correlation between age and effective time management skills, indicating that as individuals mature, they tend to become better at prioritizing and managing their time (Adams & Blair, 2019; Grissom et al., 2015). Adult students often have established life goals and responsibilities, which can motivate them to prioritize their studies and manage their time efficiently to balance their commitments (Wlodkowski & Ginsberg, 2017).

Recommendations

With respect to gender and age differences, the results point to useful ramifications for time management skill-improving treatments. Programs that teach students how to prioritize activities, set objectives, and control distractions, for instance, may help people be more satisfied with their lives, especially in high-stress situations like the job or school. Furthermore, gradually promoting a stronger sense of perceived control may lessen the stress that frequently fuels worry and burnout. Nevertheless, there are a number of restrictions on this study. Due to the sample's restriction to college and university students, it might not accurately represent the experiences of people in other age or occupation categories. This study could be extended in the future by incorporating a wider range of demographics and taking into account other elements like personality qualities or the use of technology in time management.

Conclusion

It was found that female students seem to demonstrate better time management behavior and exhibited better life satisfaction than male students. Adults students exhibited higher scores on time management behavior and life satisfaction than adolescent students. Therefore, this study adds to the expanding corpus of research on gender and age differences in time management, perceived control of time and satisfaction and provides useful advice for enhancing the wellbeing of students.

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